

1st Assessment on Micro Frontends

Provide your personal information and answer the questions on the following pages about the Nubank website.

What is your full name? *

In this exercise, you will need to access two documents: *

- Description of the proposed architecture to implement the website using Micro Frontends
- Slides from the lecture on best practices and examples of Micro Frontends

Access the architecture description of Nubank

Access the lecture slides on best practices and examples of Micro Frontends

Architectural Inspection

Assume you are a Junior Developer who is about to start working at Nubank. You have just learned more about the system architecture and were asked to analyze the MFE architecture:

Would you model the system using Micro Frontends differently? Would you keep the same MFEs, create new ones, or modify the existing ones? Also consider the screens and fragments.

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at nubank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Suppose that mfe-loan is updated and now the loan section fragment requires a new mandatory parameter: the user's current account balance. mfe-loan is deployed (sent to

production), and the app's home screen, which imports this fragment in mfe-home, starts showing an error because it was not updated to pass the new parameter to the fragment.

Loan Section Fragment

What would you do to ensure that the deployment of mfe-loan does not cause an error in the home screen, allowing the screen's code to be updated later in a gradual and safe manner?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at nubank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Consider the following communication flow between mfe-digital-account, mfe-loan, and mfe-home:

1. When a Pix transfer is successfully completed, mfe-digital-account calls a function received as a parameter from mfe-home to update the account balance displayed on the home screen.
2. mfe-home updates the account balance and modifies the parameter passed to the loan section fragment from mfe-loan.
3. mfe-loan then reprocesses and recalculates the loan offer based on the user's current balance.

Currently, there is a difficulty in updating this flow because a change may impact the communication among all fragments. How would you increase the independence between the MFEs while maintaining communication among them?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at nubank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Suppose that every time you make a change to mfe-cards, you need to access the server where the application is deployed and manually upload the code changes. Note that the deployment could be done through an automated command sequence. How would you ensure that new code deployments are not done manually?

Evolução e correção de bugs

Responda como você resolveria a tarefa abaixo considerando que você é um desenvolvedor trabalhando no Nubank. Sinta-se livre para propor novos MFEs, bibliotecas compartilhadas, telas e/ou fragmentos, além de alterar os já existentes.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Suppose that the app's home screen, implemented in mfe-home, displays an error that is not related to any component implemented directly on the page, indicating that it may originate from one of the screen's fragments. What would you do to ensure that an error in a fragment does not make the entire screen unavailable?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at nubank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Consider that mfe-investment is being treated as the module responsible for offering various investment products. It started as a module exclusively for CDB and has now been adjusted to allow investments in Treasury Bonds. Nubank wants to implement a new investment model that works very differently from CDB and Treasury Bonds (it has specific screens and a distinct purchase flow). This implementation will be problematic because the

mfe-investment code is too specific to how CDB and Treasury Bond purchases work, and adding a new product will not be easy. What would you have done during the development of the CDB and Treasury Bond flows to make mfe-investment more generic and facilitate the implementation of new investment products?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at nubank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Nubank is launching a new form of investment, NuCoin, the app's own currency that users accumulate by making credit card purchases. The feature is composed of several screens and fragments, some of which are listed below:

Main screen

NuCoin statement screen

Screen detailing raffles

Benefits screen

What architectural changes are necessary for the development of the components above?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at nubank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Nubank is launching a new feature called "Put Everything on Credit," where Pix transfers and bill payments can be made using the credit card. Additionally, one-time credit card purchases can also be paid in installments. This feature includes the following visual components:

Screen to choose what to put on credit

Screen that displays one-time purchases that can be paid in installments

Fragment with the option to pay Pix in installments

What architectural changes are necessary for the development of the components above?

Evolution and Bug Fixing

Answer how you would solve the task below, considering that you are a developer working at nubank. Feel free to propose new MFEs, shared libraries, screens, and/or fragments, as well as modify existing ones.

Note: consider the architecture described in the PDF document, without including the changes you proposed in the architectural inspection.

Consider that you have finished implementing a new MFE and now need to deploy it and connect it with other MFEs in production. You encounter many difficulties during this process and realize that they are recurring issues. How could you streamline the deployment of a new MFE next time?

Finalization

To conclude, answer the question below (it will not impact your grade, so feel free to answer honestly).

Assign a score from 0 to 5 (a real number) to reflect your perception of your knowledge about Micro Frontends: